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Principals' Awareness of Child's Rights Act for Effective Students' Administration in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Osun State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined principals' awareness of child's right act for effective student' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The design of this study was descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised all 1,423 principals in the private and public secondary schools in Osun State. The study sampled 384 respondents using a stratified random sampling technique. The instrument that was used to collect data for the study was a well-structured questionnaire titled; Principals' Awareness of Child's Right Act for Effective Student's Administration Questionnaire (PACRAESAQ) which was validated by the researcher's supervisor and two other experts in the field of Educational Measurement and Evaluation, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt. To obtain the reliability of the instrument, test re-test method was used with a reliability co-efficient of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-ratio was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed amongst others that to a very high extent private and public-school principals needed to be aware of child's right act for effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State. The study concluded that an awareness of the child's right act by principals of secondary schools enhanced the effective administration of students in private and public secondary schools in Osun State. It was recommended amongst others that the ministry of education should organize seminars on child's right act for principals and teachers of public secondary schools in Osun State.

Keywords: Child's right act, principals' awareness, secondary schools

INTRODUCTION

Education is an instrument of development and remains the most potent instrument for change. Education refers to the process by which an individual is assisted in attaining his potentials through the inculcation of values, skills, knowledge and competencies which enable him to live, adapt and contribute meaningfully to his society. This has resulted to the educational system being under constant and continuous development and transformation geared towards sustainability and improvement of the society and at the same achievement of predetermined goals of the educational system. Education could be seen as the acquisition of what is worthwhile. It is seen to focus on inculcating positive values, attitudes, beliefs and norms. Similarly, educated individuals are recognized as essential catalyst for an economy. Educated and healthy people possess the ability to make meaningful contributions to the growth of an economy. The tendencies to develop educated individuals

depend on the nature or quality of its educational system in terms of educational delivery. Perhaps, this would have formed the basis for planning education to ensure that there is quality delivery in order to satisfy the need and aspiration of the society through effective administration, management and implementation of various educational policies. According to Akinsolu (2019) education appears to be a mystical instrument that provides answers to several of the challenges in the world today. It is very crucial because it provides the human capital that steers the country's developmental process and activities. However, it is a truism that the type of human capital referred to the above can only be produced by quality education and non-mass schooling. In fact, the peculiar complete nature of the 21st century has made various demands on the education system which makes it mandatory on education to be functional and relevant otherwise the country will remain underdeveloped.

One of the most pressing issues in school administration is discipline as it concerns administrators, teachers and students. This is quite imperative because no meaningful academic achievement can be accomplished in any educational setting where there is disorder, anarchy, lack of self-control and disobedience among students. The school is not only a place of learning where knowledge is acquired but also a place where the young are disciplined in certain forms of behavioural. This is the reason most school administrators place more emphasis on discipline and control of staff and students' behaviour. Discipline is an indispensable strategic tool available to the school administrator for effective and efficient administration of the school. Discipline becomes necessary to actualize the educational objectives, but must be exercised with due considerations to the provision of the laws governing the schools. The school as a community is complex in nature and therefore laws, ordinances, edicts and disciplinary policies should be articulated and enhanced to meet and address the growing needs of checkmating the improper disciplinary behaviours that exist in our educational sector for the accomplishment of educational objectives in Nigeria.

Student disciplinary centered in our school system is a legal issue in school administration and as such care must be exercised while handling such matters. This is as a result of the legal implicating of breaching constitutional rights in the management of students' discipline as there is increase in the legal awareness levels of members of the society especially the school members to seek, enjoy and defined their rights as provided by the constitutions. In view of this, Peretomode (1990) in Kalagbor (2017) while explaining the importance of discipline under the universal principles of school administration argued that, discipline is crucial for the survival, effectiveness and efficiency of an organization. According to him, without discipline, school or organization can work smoothly and be able to achieve its set objectives, vision and mission of the school to the society. Maintenance of discipline entails using various approaches to modify students' behaviours. The first approach is non-punitive strategies such as counselling encouragement, persuasion, teaching with illustrations and presentations, scolding, etc. The second approach (often adopted when the strategies in the first approach proved ineffective) is punitive measures such as corporal punishment, suspension, expulsion, detention during school hours among other Punitive measures such as corporal punishment are often considered handy by school administrators, especially when the offence committed is grievous or callous. Callous offences such as examination malpractice, students' cult related activities, fatal stabbing, killing and rape are too serious for the principal to handle alone; they may have to report such cases to law enforcement agencies to handle in synergy with the ministry of education.

Secondary education level is very vital in the life of school aspiring students because it is the stepping stone to university education. The objectives of Post Basic Education (secondary education) as stated in National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) are to; inspire students with desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence, provide entrepreneurial, technical and vocational job specific skills for self-reliance and for agricultural, industrial, commercial and economic development, provide trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and commerce at sub-professional grade, provide holders of the basic certificate and junior Arabic and Islamic certificate with opportunity for education for higher level irrespective of gender, social status, religious or ethical background, offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities, disposition and future roles, raise morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can think independently and rationally, respect the views and feelings of others and appreciate the dignity of labour, develop and promote Nigeria languages, arts and culture in the context of world's cultural heritage, and foster patriotism, national unity and security education with emphasis on the common ties inspite of our diversity.

According to Odeh et al. (2019), school administrators constitute the main cause of the problems in schools, awareness of child rights and effective management problems inclusive. They further stressed that while both state and federal governments are determined to raise the standard of education in public secondary schools, the lack of experienced and well-trained principals continue to affect the extent of performance of secondary school education. They noted that effective administration of secondary schools largely depends on the leadership capabilities of the school administrators.

Human rights belong to all ages, sexes, classes, ethnic groups and status of human being. Irrespective of education level wealth and position in life, all humans have an inherent naturally born fundamental freedoms and rights. It is assured that the education of Nigerian child requires that all hands should be on deck. A child is any person (male or female) under eighteen (18) years of age. According to the National Policy on Education (2014), "in every action concerning a child, whether taken by an individual, public, private, institutions of service, court of law, or administrative, legislative authority, the best interest of the child must be the basic consideration". The child Right Act of 2003 as put forward by the United Nation's convention on the Rights of the child is an essential agreement by all countries that have promised to protect children's rights and Nigeria is a signatory. Child rights contribute to the children learning and confidence building in schools (secondary school inclusive). Education is the right of the children with other rights including family life, play and recreation, protection from abuse and harm and provision of healthcare besides give access to information. There are twelve basic rights of children in schools and notable ones include; education, identity, privacy, reparation, government responsibility, non-discrimination, family affiliation, protection from harm, and free wills to think.

According to UNICEF (2012), children's rights are incorporated as legally international instrument with full range of human right, civil, cultural, political, economic and social rights. "Rights" (children rights inclusive) are legal, social or ethical principles that guaranteed freedom and entitlement. Therefore, children rights are important in schools. Though, rights vary considerably around the world, but there are obvious similarities. It is assured that the principal is expected to have self-awareness, social awareness, and organizational awareness which go with students' rights. For the principal to be aware of child's rights in school, certain social skills of awareness such as; asking questions, observing body languages, listening actively and adjusting communication to different contexts are needed. The realization of children's rights can only be achieved through proper care and control of school administrators. Principal's awareness of children's rights will enable him to talk to staff (teaching and non-teaching) to protect learner's rights, talk to the children at devotion, in class and during seminars, workshops, orientations and talk to their parents. Osuji (2021) reported that students' rights in school are; right to be valued as individual with peculiar learning styles so as to maximize their potentials; right to be located fairly and with respect; access to school network services; expect learning programme that meet their needs and provided with exemplary role models among others.

The school principal is the head of the staff and there is absolute need for him to be conscious of actions of students, behaviour of students, staff and people within the school environment. The need to have the knowledge or understanding that the child in school has certain inalienable rights is very important to the principal and entire staff of the school. To this end, awareness is seen as the state of being conscious or sensitive to actions or behaviours of people or situations. It is also defined as the ability to directly know, understand, and be cognizant of behavioural actions events, personality and rights of the students and other staff personnel.

Problem

Effective school management has attracted several meanings and interpretations all over the world. Central to the notions, is the belief that a school is said to be effectively managed when it is able to maintain good human relationships such that the school work environment is described as being friendly. It is also a common belief that only when the school environment is friendly that the goals of education can be achieved. Realization of the school friendly environment is only actualized when the rights of the persons found in the school system is identified and granted to them by those who manage the school. Awareness of child's right is therefore a correlate of a friendly environment that can usher the school to attain set educational goals. Unfortunately, not all school administrators are aware that it is a call to duty to be aware of what constitutes the rights of students.

It has been observed that school administrators spend most of their working times in their offices, attending to staff issues, community problems, board matters, ministry of education, hence, they have little attention on student's issues, behaviours and actions. This may also be as a result that subordinate staffs (teachers) are available to instruct and discipline students. Students are found to cause problems in their classes, at devotion ground or assembly, during labour and other school activities. When the problems are beyond the prefects, teachers and respective vice principals, the principal comes in and order for general or mass punishment at extreme cases. One student's misconduct can result to general punishment.

The crux of the matter is that, principals order for corporal punishment on students, collect legal and illegal levies, get involved in sexual harassment with students etc. In most cases, principals do not consider that only one, two or three students caused a particular problem. Punishment is given to all students and the rights of other students are not protected. Some school principals do suspend students for weeks, months and even indefinitely on matters such as disobedience to teachers or bullying of fellow students. This suspension cannot reward the student positively, considering the gravity of offence when properly handed. It is on these premises that the researcher intends to investigate principals' awareness of child's right act for effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.

Objectives

The aim of this study was to investigate principals' awareness of child's right act for effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State. Specifically, the objectives of this study were to;

1. Investigate the extent to which principals are aware of child's right act on students' right to life for effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.
2. Examine the extent to which principals are aware of child's right act on freedom of learning for effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- To what extent does principals' awareness of child's right act on students' right to life enhance effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State?
- To what extent does principals' awareness of child's right act on freedom of learning enhance effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals from public and private secondary schools on the extent to which principal awareness of child's right act on students' right to life enhance effective students' administration in Osun State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals from public and private secondary schools on the extent to which principal awareness of child's right act on freedom of learning enhance effective students' administration in Osun State.

Fundamental Human Rights for Effective Students' Administration

The existence, validity and content of human rights continue to be the subject of debate in all aspects of education. However, it is defined in both domestic and international laws, and there is a great difference between how human rights and norms are perceived and defined in various ways both in context and content in different countries of the world. Fundamental human right has become a global issue are generally regarded as sets of legal protections, where in the context of legal systems. Such rights therefore belong without presumption or cost of privilege to all human beings under such jurisdiction. The concept of human right has been promoted as a legal concept in large part owing to the idea that human beings have such "fundamental" rights. According to Ukegbu et al. (2021), fundamental human rights are the basic natural rights which are essential for human existence and every citizen is entitled to them and is expected to enjoy them in full without discrimination or hindrance. The Nigeria constitution has several articles as fundamental human rights of man. They include: the right to life, right to dignity of human persons, the right to fair hearing, the right to personal liberty as well as right to peaceful assembly (Nwandike and Kalu, 2018). According to them, fundamental

human rights are better backed up by the constitution of the land and that the theory of constitution as a superior law is well known. They further stressed that the courts apply the constitution as law to the cases before them but they do not enforce any law which, in their opinion is forbidden by the constitution. Mejieobi (2014) reported that certain rights are perceived as sacrosanct, basic divine, natural and fundamental to the very existence of man in a civilized society and therefore be deprived or subjected to reckless abuse or infringement. This has made the attainment of equal rights to remain a constant struggle.

The concept of human rights deals with small subset of values that should be available for implementation by individuals or government. These values are clearly stated in the constitution and are based on the legal and political traditions of every country including Nigeria. Therefore, it is not a thing of surprise that the Nigeria constitution contains fundamental rights which constitute alienable and supreme rights of the individuals. In countries, like Canada, the Charter of Rights and Freedom outlines four fundamental freedoms as; freedom of conscience and religion, freedom of thought belief, opinion and expression, press and other media of communication, freedom of peaceful assembly, and freedom of association.

Also, in the United States, fundamental rights have special significance under the 14th amendment of the constitution. Thus, all human beings are endowed by their creator with certain inalienable rights, among these being rights to life, liberty and the pursuit of happiness. In Nigeria also, as earlier noted by the researcher, Sections 32-42 of Chapter IV of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, is enshrined the fundamental human rights of the citizen (FRN, 1999).

In view of these notions, fundamental human rights are the basic universal inalienable rights which should be enjoyed by all human beings regardless of their religion, ethnic, gender, race and status. In other words, fundamental human rights are rights that belong to all human beings and citizen of a country. The concept of fundamental human rights held inalienable and belongs to all human and that is why rights are clearly written in the constitutions of nations, they are necessary for freedom and rights to the maintenance of a reasonable quality of life. For example, it can be seen in the United State constitution of 1983, French Declaration of Right of Man and the Citizen in 1793, besides Nigerian constitution of 1999.

Lastly, it is imperative that school principals and teachers should have adequate knowledge of the constitutional rights of the citizen especially that of the students. It is in this light that Peretomode (2012) posited that fundamental human rights stem from the fact that they determine the constitutionality or legality of all laws, rules and regulations with government in which an educational authority may produce from time to time to time and organization of the school system.

Child Rights Act

Humans have developmental stages, anchored on birth and puberty. Age limit is an essential tool in the placement of an individual. A child is an individual within the developmental period of infancy and puberty. Reasoning on the nature of the child, Rathus (2020) described the child as a minor person or younger person than the age of the majority. One sees the child as a human being who is unable to make decisive decisions for himself or herself. According to the United Nations convention on the Rights of the child, a child is defined as "human being believes eighteen years of age". Child's Right Act (2016) reported that, one hundred and ninety-two (192) out of one hundred and ninety four (194) members of the body (Nigeria inclusive) has accepted the notion that a child is human being below the age of 18 years. Hornby (2011) defined a child as a young human who is not yet an adult, a person who is strongly influenced by the notions and attitudes of a particular time or person.

Basically, there are four rings of child protection namely, the family, community, state and international community. Similarly, child right protective environment is; family, culture and norms and legislation. The convention on the Rights of the Child (2016) put forward some basic rights of the child and these include, sharing thoughts freely, respect for children's views, freedom of the thought religion, protection of privacy, access to information, setting up or joining groups, protection from violence, responsibility of parcels, social and economic help, access to education, food clothing, and a safe home, protection from harmful work, protection from harmful drugs, protection from sexual abuse, prevention of sale and trafficking, protection from exploitation, health, water and environment, rest, play culture and arts, protection from discrimination, protection from kidnapping, etc.

Though, the aforementioned rights are numerous and it is perceived that a child in senior secondary school is still within the age bracket of 18 years. However, awareness of the principal to these rights is crucial to the better attainment of these rights of the child since it cuts across the family, community institution and organizations. According to Oraka (2018), child rights have violations, especially by developing countries (Nigeria inclusive). He added that, despite the wide acceptance and approval of the child rights act as put forward by the United Nations convention of the rights of the child by 196 countries in 1989, children all over the world are continuously abused, neglected, exploited and deprived of these rights in terms of civil, political, social economic health and cultural rights.

. Aja-Nwachukwu and Nwogbo-Egwu (2016) reported that, section 277 of the child's right act of 2003 declared that, "a child" is anyone below eighteen (18) years of age and the baskets of rights include;

1. Child's right to life, good health, balance nutrition and key household practices.
2. The child's development of his/her body, spirit and soul
3. Child's protection from labour, ritual killing, trafficking, physical sexual, emotional abuses besides neglect, and
4. Child's right to be involved in matters that concern him as in Section 3(1), (2), 6,7,8,13,19 and 20. They added that a person that have sexual intercourse with a female child commits rape offence and is liable for life imprisonment conviction (child right act 2003, section 31, subsection 1). Similarly, Taiwo (2021) posited that the four brackets of child's right are as written below;
5. Successive government, local, state and federal levels are to reduce child's mortality rate, provide better medical health care, adequate feeding and safe drinking water, hygienic and sanitized environments, combat contacted diseases and malnutrition, support and mobilize through local and community resources, the development of primary healthcare for them.
6. Child's freedom from discrimination for belonging to a particular community, ethnic group, place of origin, sex, religion, birth disability, deprivation or political opinion while the dignity of the child must always be respected.
7. No child in Nigeria should be subjected to physical, mental, emotional injury, abuse or neglect, maltreatment, fortune, in human or degrading punishment, attack on his/her honour or reputation. Hence, every Nigerian child is entitled to adequate rest, leisure and enjoyment in the best state of mental, physical and spiritual health.
8. Every Nigerian child should be well protected.

Finally, the notion of the childhood is a tinker for the application of various principles in diverse aspects of life including criminal law, contract, property, family, institutional and international law.

Awareness of Childs' Right Act

Awareness is the state of consciousness, realization and knowledge of something. It is believed that awareness of one type of idea or issue naturally fosters an awareness of another idea. Ukala (2018) saw awareness as knowledge or understanding of a particular subject or situation. It could be an awareness of the environment, politics and social situations. Awareness is seen as the ability to notice something using one's senses, and the attribute of action.

To Schmidt (2019) awareness is an integrated aspect of practice and must be investigated as such. According to him, awareness is the state or ability to perceive, to feel, or to be conscious of events, or sensory patterns. Moreso, awareness is the state or quality of being aware of something. In this context, awareness does not refer to some special category of mental state existing independently of action, but a person being or becoming aware of something. In the same vein, Nakpodia (2015) posited that in Nigeria, there is the awareness of increased attention given to individuals' right especially those described as fundamental rights of the citizens. This fundamental right of the citizen is applicable to the students. Peretomode (2019) advised that students right should be safe guided to enable students understand the legal aspect of education, learn the basic principle of law and develop some degree of competence in applying them to educational problems and also recognize situation in which it is not safe to proceed without competent legal advice.

Principals' Awareness of Childs' Rights Act

In the organization of the Public Secondary Education System, both the Junior Secondary Section and Senior Secondary Section have administrative or leadership heads as captured through the statutory functions of the principal as outlined in the National Policy of Education (2014). It is assured that he or she has the knowledge, perception, concern and development consciousness of the staff and students. In fact, the presence of the students in public and private secondary schools in Ondo State and other states in Nigeria is the reason for teachers' role, execution of their duties and principals attending to daily duties in their schools. It is believed that the school administrator carries forth leadership, ordination and direction roles within the school environment. National Policy on Education (2014) also stated that the broad goals of secondary education shall be to prepare the child for, useful living written the society, and higher education. Based on the comprehensive nature of the secondary school curriculum, principals' awareness of child's right is prerequisite for;

6. Inspiring students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence.
7. Foster national unity with the aim to build common ties that will unite him or her in our diversity.
8. Raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate human values specified under the broad national goals and live as good citizens

Right to Life for Effective Students' Administration

Human rights act stipulated that everyone has the right to life. In particular, no one may be arbitrarily deprived of life. It is applied to a person from the time of birth. Every human being, be it a day or a child teenage adult has the right to life. Ejeh (2018) posited that right to life is a term used to describe the belief that a child, teenage or adult has essential right to live. In the school setting, a lot of things happen especially in the secondary school system, students at senior levels always attempt to punish or exercise power over their junior colleagues.

Moreover, principals and teachers most times do not care about the magnitude of care or physical use of hands-on students out of anger or suspicion on a subject matter. Nakpodia (2020) expressed disappointment over a child in senior secondary school who lost his eyes due to teacher roughly locating the child all over the body, in an attempt to defend excess caning, his two eyes were damaged. Notwithstanding, Dagogo (2015) pointed out some of fundamental rights of the child in secondary school (senior secondary inclusive) that has been meted on children which include; corporal punishment, deforming students' personality by cutting of uniform arbitrarily, preventing students from writing examination they have registered for, suspension and expulsion of the child without trial or advance information, and interfering into private life of students by way of unauthorized searches and medical test. He noted that, school administrators in both junior and senior secondary schools made students to be unsecured, unstable, frustrated, ineffective during classes on learning and this results to poor academic performance. He further stressed that in this complex world, dangerous happenings, and actions take place in almost all human environment. Right to life means that nobody neither male nor female besides the government or any human organizations have the right to terminate or end a child's or any other human being's life. Hence, it is the sole responsibility of the government at local, state and federal levels in Nigeria to protect human life, children's lives inclusive.

Human Rights Commission (2020) reported that, both child right act and human right act protect the right to life of every individual irrespective of age, sex, religion, status and race. The commission noted that, right to life is based on preventing the arbitrary deprivation of life and relevant in situation including; the use of force by public authorities, the delivery of medical treatment, and investigating on the conduct of public entities especially when a person dies while in their care. It is believed that every person has the right to have his life protected.

Freedom of Learning for Effective Students' Administration

Students in Senior Secondary School levels are involved in serious learning as they are preparing for external examinations including West African Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and Joint Admission Matriculation Board Examination (JAMB) or University Tertiary Examination. However,

setbacks may arise in the course of their learning in their schools. At times students in both junior and senior secondary school levels are kept from possessing, enjoying and attending classes or participation in teaching – learning processes. Deprivation according to Hornby (2011) is an act or instance of withholding or taking something away from someone or something. Deprivation of learning is a term used to describe when students are overwhelmed by the conditions of poverty, scarcity of financial resources and restraint from participation in the teaching-learning processes in the classroom. Therefore, the rights of a child in this section posits that a child has right to free, compulsory and Universal Basic Education and it shall be the duty of the government in Nigeria to provide such education.

According to Ajibola and Ali (2018), every school administrator is committed to ensuring that students in their schools are provided with safe and orderly environment for teaching and learning. Deprivation of learning by students can be attributed to school and non-school factors. The non-school factors include;

- i. Ill-health of the student
- ii. Family income or financial status of parents
- iii. Student deliberate refusal to learn or attend classes
- iv. Communal crisis, and,
- v. Sending students to market or other services during school hours

However, school factors that can hinder children from learning include but not limited to;

- i. Lack of available classrooms for conducive learning.
- ii. Lack of available teachers or presence of poor trained teachers
- iii. Poor school management and discipline culture
- iv. Attending to punishment by the principal, teachers or senior colleagues.

School administrators like other leaders of public institutions are complex, having personalities peculiar to other humans. As temperature differs, controlling of temperature differs among principals as well. Some principals are pushed to take actions that will deprive students to learn. It is not surprising that order of non-payment of sport levies and failure to come to school punctual will attract punishment that will keep students away from learning. Most times, principals give punishment such as cutting of grasses which keep students off from learning during morning hours or anytime of the learning hours in school setting. Effective learning implies that the children or learners are able to understand and make use of knowledge information and skills or instructions provided by their teachers during teaching-learning processes. Yusuf and Ibrahim (2018) alerted that warning of a learning crisis in global education indicates that schooling without learning is not just a misused development chances, but a great unfairness to children or learners in general, mostly caused by school authorities or principals' infringement on students' rights. They further stated that deprivation of learning made students not to be;

5. inspired with a desire for self-improvement.
6. able to foster patriotism, national unity and proper security education.
7. able to offer later for differences in students' disposition, future roles and opportunities.
8. morally upright and well-adjusted individuals who can culture in the context of world culture heritage.
9. potential holders of certificates with chances of higher education, irrespective of social status, gender, religion or ethnic background.

It has been observed that school administrators in a attempt of maintain administrative effectiveness, go all out, class by class to see that; payment of school levies are done, school uniforms have badges and crests, school ethnical norms or values including hairstyles, dressing codes are observed, ensuring the punishment of students that do not observe extra-curricular activities are duly punished besides absence from labour and recommended textbooks including bible or hymn books for morning devotions are with students.

Biokoro (2019) revealed that, new research shows that 92 percent learning deprivation among Nigerian children are public senior secondary school levels. According to him, deprivation of learning on children in senior secondary schools was caused by both school management and non-school factors. Education News Network

(2022) reported that principal of Government Model Secondary school, PheelKhana was suspended for depriving 800 students of the school from learning after lessons due to restrictions posed on their afternoon meal which would have provided energy for attending classes. To rectify the ugly situation, the state education department had pounded the school with necessary ration in order that afternoon learning be maintained. It is assured that the importance placed on learning warranted the state education authority to suspend the principal.

Freeman's Theory of Children's Right by Michael Freeman (1983).

This theory was propounded by Michael Freeman in (1983), as cited in Jo-Boyden (2014), this theory states that children have interest that justified protection before they develop well to assert their rights. The theory focuses on the child's potential and contended that a child has right whether or not, he or she is capable of exercising them. Children are meant to have full responsibility as free, rational humans with their own systems of ends. The theory uphold that children must be accorded the right to equal opportunity and the right to liberal paternalism. This theory holds that;

3. children are active agents in their own lives and relationships, not simply passive subjects of social or biological processes.
4. children vary in time, place with class, gender and ethnicity, hence not one child but many complex children.
5. childhood is understand as a social construction not an inevitable biological state.
6. children lives are worthy of study in their own rights.
7. ethnography is a useful approach of studying children's opinions and behaviours through observation, interaction and interview directly with them not on adult report.
8. from Bible and literal views, adults construct children as helpless victims with rescuing adults or needy dependent with providing adults as naughty deviants with disciplining adults or as resourceful actors interacting with respectful adults.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study comprised of all 1,423 principals in the private and public secondary schools in Osun State. The study sampled 384 respondents using stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self structured questionnaire titled: Principals' Awareness of Child's Right Act for Effective Student's Administration Questionnaire (PACRAESAQ) which was validated by the researcher's supervisor and two other experts in the field of Educational Measurement and Evaluation, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt. In order to obtain the reliability of the instrument, test re-test method was used with a reliability co-efficient of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-ratio was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research question 1: *To what extent does principals’ awareness of child’s right act on students’ right to life enhance effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent to which Principals’ Awareness of Child’s Right Act on Students’ Right to Life Enhances Effective Students’ Administration in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Osun State

S/No	Items	Public Principals n = 131		Private Principals n = 252		Mean Set X ₁ X ₂	Decision
		Mea n X ₁	SD	Mean X ₂	SD		
1	Students have right to live	3.12	0.99	3.10	1.00	3.11	High Extent
2	Students are frustrated	3.28	0.89	3.25	0.87	3.27	Very High Extent
3	Students are unsecured	3.36	0.81	3.30	0.89	3.33	Very High Extent
4	Students are threatened by their teachers	3.43	0.65	3.23	0.79	3.33	Very High Extent
5	Teachers protect the life of their students	3.49	0.66	3.35	0.81	3.40	Very High Extent
6	Students are tortured	3.37	0.70	3.29	0.73	3.33	Very High Extent
7	Teachers kill students	3.49	0.58	3.30	0.81	3.40	Very High Extent
8	Students are beaten	3.30	0.69	3.43	0.59	3.36	Very High Extent
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		3.36	0.75	3.28	0.81	3.32	Very High Extent

Scale: 1.00– 1.79 = Very low extent (VLE), 1.80 – 2.49 = Low extent (LE), 2.50 – 3.19 = High extent (HE), and 3.20 – 4.00 = Very high extent (VHE)

Results on Table 1 show that item 1 had a mean score between the range of 2.50 and 3.19 showing a high extent. Differently, items 2 to 8, had mean scores of between 3.20 and 4.00, showing that, for those respondents, principals’ awareness of child’s right act on students’ right to life enhances effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State is to a very high extent. In summary, with an aggregate mean of 3.32 (which falls within the range of 3.20 to 4.00), public and private respondents of the study answered that principals’ awareness of child’s right act on students’ right to life enhances effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State is to a very high extent.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does principals’ awareness of child’s right act on freedom of learning enhance effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Extent Principals’ Awareness of Child’s Right Act on Freedom of Learning Enhances Effective Students’ Administration in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Osun State.

S/No	Items	Public Principals n = 131		Private Principals n = 252		Mean Set X ₁ X ₂	Decision
		Mea n X ₁	SD	Mean X ₂	SD		
9	Principal allow students to be on punishment while teaching/learning is in progress	2.91	0.89	2.95	0.84	2.93	High Extent
10	Students are scared of asking question in the class	3.22	0.82	3.16	0.91	3.19	High Extent
11	Students are punished for answering questions wrongly	3.27	0.78	3.05	0.89	3.16	High Extent
12	Students are sent out of the class for coming late to class	3.46	0.57	3.20	0.85	3.33	Very high Extent
13	Students are punished in class for noise making	3.37	0.75	3.12	0.95	3.25	Very High Extent
14	Students are denied from writing	3.24	0.90	3.11	0.87	3.18	High Extent
15	Students are sent out of the class for improper dressing	3.13	0.86	3.30	0.75	3.21	Very High Extent
16	Students are sent out due to non-payment of school fees	3.36	0.78	3.05	1.01	3.21	Very High Extent
17	Students stop coming to school due to illness	3.37	0.69	3.16	0.90	3.27	Very High Extent
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		3.26	0.80	3.13	0.89	3.20	Very High Extent

*The scale for Table 1 applies

Date on Table 2 above show that items 9, 10, 11 and 14 had a mean score between the range of 2.50 and 3.19 showing a high extent. On the other hand, items 12, 13, 15, 16 and 17, had mean scores of between 3.20 and 4.00, showing that for those respondents, principals’ awareness of child’s right act on freedom of learning enhances effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State is to a very high extent.

In summary, with an aggregate mean of 3.20 (which falls within the range of 3.20 to 4.00), public and private respondents of the study answered that principals’ awareness of child’s right act on freedom of learning enhances effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State is to a very high extent.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals from public and private secondary schools on the extent to which principal awareness of child’s right act on students’ right to life enhance effective students’ administration in Osun State.

Table 3: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Ratings of Public and Private Principals’ Awareness of Child’s Right Act on Students’ Right to Life Enhances Effective Students’ Administration in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Osun State

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Decision Significance
Public Principals	131	3.36	0.75	381	0.65	1.96	0.05 Accepted
Private Principals	252	3.28	0.81				

Legend

- dg:** degree of freedom
- z-cal.:** z-calculated value
- z-crit.:** z-critical value

Data on Table 3 show the value of z-cal. to be 0.65 while the value of z-crit. was 1.96. Since the value of z-cal. of 0.65 is less than the value of z-crit. of 1.96, the null hypothesis was accepted and this implied that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of public and private principals’ awareness of child’s right act on students’ right to life enhances effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals from public and private secondary schools on the extent to which principal awareness of child’s right act on freedom of learning enhance effective students’ administration in Osun State.

Table 4: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Ratings of Public and Private Principals’ Awareness of Child’s Right Act on Freedom of Learning Enhances Effective Students’ Administration in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Osun State.

Variable	n	Mean	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Decision Significance
Public Principals	131	3.26	0.80	381	0.59	1.96	0.05 Accepted
Private Principals	252	3.13	0.89				

*The legend for Table 4.6 applies

Data on Table 4 show the value of z-cal. to be 0.59 while the value of z-crit. was 1.96. Since the value of z-cal. of 0.59 is less than the value of z-crit. of 1.96, the null hypothesis was accepted and this implied that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of public and private principals’ awareness of child’s right act on freedom of learning enhances effective students’ administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

To what extent does principals' awareness of child's right act on students' right to life enhance effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State?

The findings of this study revealed that to a very high extent, private and public principals need to be aware of child's right act on students' right to life enhances effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State. The test of hypothesis showed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of public and private principals' awareness of child's right act on students' right to life enhances effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State. This finding is in consonance with Ejeh (2018) who stated that right to life is a term used to describe the belief that a child, teenager or adult has essential right to live. According to him, in the school setting, a lot of things happen especially in the secondary school system. Students at senior levels always attempt to punish or exercise power over their junior colleagues. Dagogo (2015) supported this view by pointing out some fundamental rights of the child in secondary school (senior secondary inclusive) that has been meted on children which include; corporal punishment, deforming students' personality by cutting of uniform arbitrarily, preventing students from writing examination they have registered for, suspension and expulsion of the child without trial or advance information, and interfering into private life of students by way of unauthorized searches and medical test. He noted that school administrators in both junior and senior secondary schools made students to be unsecured, unstable, frustrated, ineffective during classes on learning and this results to poor academic performance.

To what extent does principals' awareness of child's right act on freedom of learning enhance effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State?

The findings of this study revealed that to a very high extent, private and public principals need to be aware of child's right act on freedom of learning enhances effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State. The test of hypothesis showed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of public and private principals' awareness of child's right act on freedom of learning enhances effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.

This finding is in agreement with Ajibola and Ali (2018) who posited that every school administrator is committed to ensuring that students in their schools are provided with safe and orderly environment for teaching and learning. According to them, deprivation of learning by students can be attributed to school and non-school factors such as ill-health of the student, family income or financial status of parents, student deliberate refusal to learn or attend classes, communal crisis, and sending students to market or other services during school hours. Yusuf and Ibrahim (2018) supports this notion by stating that warning of a learning crisis in global education indicates that schooling without learning is not just a misused development chances, but a great unfairness to children or learners in general, mostly caused by school authorities or principal's infringement on students' rights.

FINDINGS

1. result of the analysis revealed that to a very high extent, principals are aware of The child's right act on students right to life for effective students' administration in the following ways; students are unsecured, students are frustrated, students are beaten, students are tortured, teachers kill students, students are threatened by their teachers, teachers protect the life of their students and students have right to life.
2. The study revealed that to a very high extent, principals are aware of child's right act on students' freedom of learning in the following ways; students are scared of asking questions in the class, principals allow students to be on punishment while learning is in progress, students are punished for answering questions wrongly, students are sent out of the class for coming late to class, students are punished in class for noise making, students are denied from writing, students are sent out of the class for improper dressing, students are sent out due to non-payment of school fees, and students stop coming to school due to illness.

3. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of public and private principals awareness of child's right act on students' right to life for effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.
4. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of public and private principals awareness of child's right act on freedom of learning for effective students' administration in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that an awareness of the child's rights act by principals' of secondary schools enhanced the effective administration of students in private and public secondary schools in Osun State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, it is recommended as follows;

1. The ministry of education should organize seminars on child's right act for principals and teachers of public secondary schools in Osun State.
2. Government should take proper measures against secondary school principals who violate the child's right act on students' right to live.

REFERENCES

- Agi, U.K. & Adiele, E.E. (2019). Educational management, (Revised edition). Harey Publication.
- Aja-Nwachukwu, M. A., & Nwogbo-Egwu, C. C. (2016). Scientific attainment of the parents of a Nigerian child: Has the Supreme Court come to terms with it? *Ebonyi State University Law Journal*, 6, 1-8.
- Ajibola, A. L., & Ali, A. H. (2018). Disciplinary measures in Nigerian senior secondary schools: Issues and prospects. *Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 4(3), 11-17.
- Biokoro, O.B. (2019). Principal's knowledge of education law in secondary school administration. *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, 89(1), 27 – 37.
- Child's Right Act (2003). *Rights and responsibilities of a child*, <http://www.placng.org>
- Dagogo, D. (2015). The legal aspects' of students' discipline. In L.D. Kalagbor (Ed.), *Education law in the context of school administration*. Pearl Publishers.
- Ejeh, P. O. (2018). Assessment of principals' violation of students rights in secondary school administration in Kogi State. Research Wap Publishers.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). National policy on education. NERDC Press.
- Hornby, A. S. (2011). Oxford advanced learner's dictionary. Oxford University Press.
- Human Rights Commission (2020). Article II: Freedom of assembly and association. UN General Secretariat. <https://5bfreedomofexpression.weeb1>
- Mezieobi, K. C. & Nzokurum, J. C. (2014). Impact of educational leadership on the Nigeria educational system. *Journal of the Association of social Educationist of Nigeria*, 74(10), 88-96.
- Nakpodia, E. D. (2011). Analysis of cases of violation of student's rights, in Delta State secondary schools in Nigeria. Department of Educational Administration and Policy Studies, Abraka University, Delta State.
- Nakpodia, E. D. (2018). Teacher's disciplinary approaches to students' discipline problems in Nigeria secondary schools. *International NGO Journal*, 5(6) 144 - 151.
- Nakpodia, E, D. (2020). An analysis of cases of violation of students' rights in Delta State secondary school, Nigeria. *Prime Research on Education*, 1(3), 50-59.
- National Assembly of Nigeria (2013). The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Vanguard Newspaper.com
- Nwadike, J. C. & Kalu, T. C. (2018). Human right and the African peoples: A case study of Nigeria (1960-1984). In C. E. Emezi, & Ndoh, C. A. (Ed), *African politics*. Achujo Publishers.
- Odeh, R.C., Oguchi, O.D. & Wagher, E.D. (2019). Influence of school environment on academic achievement of students in secondary schools in zone A senatorial district of Benue State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*, 6(7), 4914-4922.

- Oraka, O. (2018). Violations of the rights of the child: The Nigeria example. Organization for World Peace.
- Osuji, C.U. (2012). School plant management. A handbook for educational administrators. Chromnett Communications.
- Peretomode, V. E. (2019). Educational and law school administration: Concept, principles and cases. B. N. Right Integrated Publishers.
- Rathus, S. A. (2013). Childhood and adolescence: Voyages in development. Engage Learning.
- Schmidt, K. (2019). The problem with awareness of child's rights public awareness campaign project. <http://www.acerwc.org>.
- Ukaegbu, M.N., Ike, A. Adebayo, S.A., Uche, E. & Anyaoha, C.N. (2021). Basic civic education or senior secondary schools 2. Mcybiks Nigerian Publishers.
- Ukala, C.C. (2018). Students perception of discipline in public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 6(3), 35 – 50.
- UNICEF (2012). Children's well-being from their own point of view: What affects the children's well-being in the first year of compulsory secondary education in Spain? UNICEF.
- Yusuf, S., Yusufu, A. A. & Ibrahim, M. A. (2018). Addressing the factors responsible for schooling without learning in primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. *Pobrane Z Czasopisma International Journal of Synergy and Research*, 14, 17-25.